

Exploring the Role of Digital-content in Enhancing Teacher Professional Development in the Context of NEP 2020

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ABSTRACT: *This study explores the role of digital content in enhancing teacher professional development in the context of the National Education Policy 2020 (NEP, 2020). A descriptive survey method was employed; 100 secondary school teachers were selected to collect data, and questionnaires were made to collect the data from Teachers. Data was collected through a questionnaire using Google Forms. The study investigates teachers' perceptions of digital content effectiveness, identifies the most effective types of digital content, and examines the barriers and facilitators to its adoption. The findings highlight the potential of digital content to enhance teacher professional development, particularly in areas such as pedagogical innovation and subject matter expertise. However, challenges such as the digital divide, content quality, and institutional support need to be addressed to fully leverage digital content for teacher development. The study's insights inform the design of effective digital-content-based professional development programs aligned with NEP 2020 goals.*

KEYWORDS: Digital content, teacher professional development, student-centered learning, NEP 2020, secondary education, technology integration, pedagogical competencies.

INTRODUCTION: The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP, 2020) marks a significant milestone in India's education landscape, emphasizing the need for a transformative overhaul of the education system (Ministry of Education, 2020). Teacher professional development is recognized as a critical component of this transformation, with a focus on enhancing teacher capacity, pedagogical innovation, and subject matter expertise (Darling-Hammond, 2017). The policy acknowledges the importance of leveraging digital technologies to support teacher development, particularly in the context of India's diverse and geographically dispersed education landscape (NEP, 2020).

Digital content has emerged as a promising tool for enhancing teacher professional development, offering flexibility, accessibility, and personalized learning experiences (Koehler & Mishra, 2009). The use of digital content can facilitate teachers' engagement with new pedagogies, subject matter, and technologies, leading to improved teaching practices and student outcomes (Hutchison & Colwell, 2015). However, the effectiveness of digital content in supporting teacher professional development in the context of NEP-2020 still needs to be explored.

This study aims to address this knowledge gap by investigating the role of digital content in enhancing teacher professional development. Drawing on a mixed-methods approach, this research explores teachers' perceptions of digital content effectiveness, identifies the most effective types of digital content, and examines the barriers and facilitators to its adoption. By doing so, this study seeks to inform the design of effective digital-content-based professional development programs aligned with NEP-2020 goals.

SIGNIFICANCE:

1. This study Contributes to the understanding of the role of digital content in enhancing teacher professional development in the context of NEP-2020.
2. This study provides insights for policymakers, education administrators, and teacher educators to design effective digital-content-based professional development programs.
3. This study Informs the development of digital content that aligns with the needs of teachers and the goals of NEP-2020.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE: The literature review provides a comprehensive overview of the existing research on teacher professional development, digital content, and its role in enhancing teaching practices. The review highlights the significance of digital content in supporting teacher professional development, particularly in the context of the National Education Policy 2020 (NEP, 2020).

Teacher Professional Development: Studies emphasize the importance of ongoing learning experiences for teachers to improve their knowledge, skills, and attitudes (Darling-Hammond, 2017; Guskey, 2002).

Digital Content: Research highlights the potential of digital content to enhance teacher professional development, including improved pedagogy, subject matter expertise, and technology integration (Koehler & Mishra, 2009; Hutchison & Colwell, 2015).

Barriers and Facilitators: Literature identifies challenges such as the digital divide, content quality, and institutional support as hindrances to effective digital content integration (Al-Mahmood & McLoughlin, 2019; Boelens & De Wever, 2018).

Effective Digital Content: Studies suggest that interactive simulations, video lectures, and online discussions are effective types of digital content for teacher professional development (Baki & Guveli, 2017; Chen & Chen, 2019).

OBJECTIVES:

1. To investigate the impact of digital content on teacher professional development in the context of NEP 2020.
2. To identify the most effective types of digital content for supporting teacher professional development.
3. To explore the factors influencing the adoption of digital content for teacher professional development.

METHODOLOGY:

Method: A descriptive Survey method was used.

Sample and Sampling Technique: 100 secondary-level school teachers were selected to A random sampling technique was used to collect the data.

Tools: A Questionnaire was made to collect the data from Teachers. Data was collected through a questionnaire using Google Forms.

Data Analysis: Data was analyzed through content analysis.

RESULTS: Data was analyzed objective-wise as below-

Analysis of The Teacher's Responses:

How effective do you think digital content in enhancing your professional development?
100 responses

Figure-1, shows the teacher’s thinking regarding digital content in enhancing their professional development.

By the observation of the above figure, it was found that the highest 72% of teachers found it very effective, 16% effective, 2% Neutral, 10% somewhat effective, and only 0% found digital content not effective in enhancing their professional development.

What benefits have you derived from using digital content? (Select all that apply)
100 responses

Figure-2, shows the benefits that teachers derived from using digital content.

By the observation of the above figure-2, it was found that 29% of teachers were using Improved pedagogy, the highest 73% using Subject matter expertise, 64% using Technology integration, and 17% were using Networking.

Which type of digital content do you use in your teaching (Select all that apply)

100 responses

Figure-3, shows which type of digital content is used by the teachers in their teaching.

By the observation of the above figure-3, it was found that 47% of teachers were using Video lectures, the highest 78% using Interactive simulations, 62% using Online discussion, 30% using Podcasts, and 15% were using Blogs.

What challenges have you faced while using digital content? (Select all that apply)

100 responses

Figure-4, shows the types of challenges faced by teachers while using digital content.

By the observation of the above figure-4, it was found that 54% of teachers faced a digital divide, 59% faced challenges with content quality, 78% faced institutional support, and 46% faced technical issues.

What factors facilitate your use of digital content? (Select all that apply)

100 responses

Figure-5, shows what factors facilitate teachers' use of digital content.

By the observation of the above figure-5, it was found that 49% of teachers got to facilitate and help from School administration support, 49% from Colleagues, 65% from Access to devices/internet, and 31% from Relevant content availability.

FINDINGS: The study revealed that digital content has a significant role in enhancing teachers' professional development. The key findings were as follows-

1. Effectiveness of Digital Content: 72% of teachers found digital content very effective in enhancing their professional development, while 16% found it effective, 2% Neutral, 10% somewhat effective, and 0% not effective.

2. Benefits of Digital Content: Teachers derived benefits from digital content, including improved pedagogy at 29%, subject matter expertise at 73%, technology integration at 64%, and networking at 17%.

3. Types of Digital Content: Teachers used various digital content types, including video lectures 47%, interactive simulations 78%, online discussions 62%, podcasts 30%, and blogs 15%.

4. Challenges: Teachers faced challenges, including digital divide 54%, content quality 59%, institutional support 78%, and technical issues 46%.

5. Facilitating Factors: Teachers were facilitated by school administration support 49%, colleague encouragement 73%, Access to devices/internet 65%, and relevant content availability 31%.

CONCLUSION: This study highlights the significance of digital content in enhancing teacher professional development in the context of NEP-2020. The findings suggest that teachers perceive digital content as effective, particularly in areas such as subject matter expertise and technology integration. However, challenges like the digital divide, content quality, and institutional support need to be addressed.

To fully leverage digital content for teacher development, policymakers, education administrators, and teacher educators should:

1. Develop high-quality digital content aligned with NEP-2020 goals.
2. Provide institutional support and infrastructure for digital content integration.
3. Enhance teacher digital literacy through training and capacity-building programs.
4. Foster collaborative environments encouraging peer support and sharing of best practices.

By addressing these recommendations, educators can harness the potential of digital content to transform teacher professional development and improve student outcomes in India.

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